

Morpholine Dithiocarbamate and Propylene Diamine Complexes of Cu(III) and Ni(III)

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Eleven complexes of trivalent copper and nickel of the types $\text{Cu}(\text{mdtc})_3$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{mdtc})_3]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I ; $\text{mdtc} = \text{morpholine dithiocarbamate}$), $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Br}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Br} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{pn} = \text{propylene diamine}$) have been isolated by oxidation of $\text{M}(\text{mdtc})_2/\text{M}(\text{pn})_2\text{X}_2$ with halogen in suitable media. They were characterised by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectral data. The existence of an equilibrium mixture of diamagnetic square planar and paramagnetic tetrahedral forms in the same crystalline substance is suggested for all the copper(III) complexes. Rare examples of low spin complexes of nickel(III) having square planar geometry are provided by complexes of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{mdtc})_3]\text{X}$. Low spin propylene diamine complexes of nickel(III) show octahedral stereochemistry around nickel(III) ion.

THE coordination chemistry of higher valent copper and nickel ions has not received so much attention as that of their divalent ions. Several copper(II) complexes containing dithiocarbamate¹⁻³ and nickel(II) complexes with phosphorous and arsenic donor ligands^{4,5}, ethylene diamine⁶, biguanide and guanlyl urea⁷ and dithiocarbamate² have been reported to undergo oxidation on reaction with halogens. However, the reactions with halogens of the complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) containing the ligands under study, do not appear to have been studied earlier. The present investigation reports the isolation and characterisation of eleven novel oxidation products of morpholine dithiocarbamate, and propylene diamine complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) with halogens.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were B.D.H.(L.R.) grade. Sodium salt of morpholine dithiocarbamate was prepared according to the reported method⁸. The starting complexes, $\text{Cu}/\text{Ni}(\text{mdtc})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{pn})_2\text{Br}_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ were isolated by standard methods.

Synthesis of complexes :

Chlorination : Dry chlorine gas was bubbled very slowly through a suspension of well powdered complexes, $\text{M}(\text{mdtc})_2$ or $\text{M}(\text{pn})_2\text{X}_2$, in CCl_4 with constant shaking till a small change in colour of the suspension was just noticed. It was then stirred by a magnetic stirrer for about 30 min to ensure complete reaction.

Bromination/iodination : Very dilute solution of bromine/iodine in carbon disulphide was added dropwise to a suspension of well powdered complex, $\text{M}(\text{mdtc})_2$ or $\text{M}(\text{pn})_2\text{X}_2$, in carbon disulphide with constant stirring by means of a magnetic stirrer till a

change in colour of the suspension was noticed. The resulting suspension was then stirred for 30 min more to ensure complete oxidation. The separated complexes were suction filtered, washed with CCl_4 or CS_2 followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo*.

Analyses and physical measurements : The complexes were analysed for metal, sulphur and halogen gravimetrically by standard methods. Molar conductance of the complexes in methanol at 10^{-3} M was measured by a Systronic direct reading conductometer, type 303. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens at room temperature by a Gouy balance. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 397 in KBr pellet in $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform were recorded using an Elico, model CL 24 spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of the complexes are presented in Table 1 and the infrared and electronic spectral data are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and molar conductance data indicate the formation of the complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{mdtc})_3$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{mdtc})_3]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I), $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Br}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{pn})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Br} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The electrolytic and non-electrolytic nature of the above formulations are amply indicated by their Δ_{M} values (Table 1). These complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are sparingly soluble in methanol and chloroform. All the nickel complexes reported in this investigation liberate iodine from KI in acid medium showing the presence of higher oxidation state of the nickel ion. Had there been substitution in the ligands by halogens instead of

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, COLOUR, MELTING POINT, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Compound	Colour	m p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M (mhos)
			Metal	Sulphur	Halogen		
1. Cu(mdtc)Cl ₂	Bottle green	> 250	21.20 (21.42)	21.60 (21.59)	23.65 (23.95)	1.53	7.5
2. Cu(mdtc)Br ₂	Bottle green	222	16.55 (16.47)	16.55 (16.60)	41.80 (41.45)	1.55	8.8
3. Cu(mdtc)I ₂	Brownish green	> 250	13.01 (13.25)	13.25 (13.36)	53.40 (52.95)	1.57	10.5
4. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]Cl	Greenish yellow	> 250	13.60 (14.04)	29.88 (30.61)	8.40 (8.49)	2.47	130
5. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]Br	Greenish yellow	> 250	12.15 (12.69)	27.01 (27.67)	16.85 (17.27)	2.35	125
6. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]I	Brownish green	> 250	11.05 (11.52)	24.60 (25.12)	24.01 (24.91)	2.37	135
7. [Ni(pn) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.2H ₂ O	Deep violet	230	16.50 (16.81)	—	30.84 (30.49)	2.41	150
8. [Ni(pn) ₂ Cl ₂]Br.2H ₂ O	Deep violet	> 250	15.01 (14.91)	—	Cl-18.35(18.04) Br-20.01(20.30)	2.32	146
9. [Cu(pn)Cl ₂]Cl	Light green	233	25.80 (26.02)	—	43.70 (43.64)	1.65	126
10. [Cu(pn)Cl ₂]Br	Light blue	238	22.00 (22.02)	—	Cl-24.80(24.62) Br-27.50(27.70)	1.68	130
11. [Cu(pn)Br ₂]Br	Green	205	16.95 (16.84)	—	63.95 (63.56)	1.70	142

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF Cu(III) AND Ni(III)

Compound	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu_{as}(C-S)$	$\nu(M-S)$	$\nu(N-H)$	$\nu(M-N)$	Electronic spectra (nm)
1. Cu(mdtc)Cl ₂	1500 s	1010 s	400 w	—	—	440, 585, 880
2. Cu(mdtc)Br ₂	1498 s	1015 m	400 w	—	—	420, 590, 890
3. Cu(mdtc)I ₂	1490 m	1010 w	405 w	—	—	430, 605, 895
4. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]Cl	1500 m	1010 s	410 m	—	—	385, 660, 860
5. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]Br	1500 s	1010 s	410 m	—	—	395, 665, 870
6. [Ni(mdtc) ₂]I	1498 s	1010 m	405 m	—	—	390, 660, 870
7. [Ni(pn) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl.2H ₂ O	—	—	—	3300 br, 3240 m	432 m	400, 430, 625
8. [Ni(pn) ₂ Cl ₂]Br.2H ₂ O	—	—	—	3280 br, 3170 m	430 m	405, 435, 635
9. [Cu(pn)Cl ₂]Cl	—	—	—	3300 s, 3230 m	435 w	380, 580, 880
10. [Cu(pn)Cl ₂]Br	—	—	—	3300 s, 3230 s	435 m	385, 575, 875
11. [Cu(pn)Br ₂]Br	—	—	—	3290 s, 3235 s	430 s	375, 570, 875

s=sharp, m=medium, w=weak and br=broad.

oxidation of the metal ions, the compositions, elemental analyses and the magnetic moments of the complexes under report would have been different. All the complexes are very stable, except [Ni(pn)₂Cl₂]Br.2H₂O which decomposes gradually after a week.

Magnetic moments: It has been reported¹⁻³ that oxidation of the complexes of the type Cu(dtc)₂ by halogens results in the formation of diamagnetic planar complexes (μ_{eff} values ~ 0.5 B.M.) having composition [Cu(dtc)X₂]. But in the present investigation all the trivalent copper complexes have magnetic moments ranging from 1.53 to 1.70 B.M. which show an appreciable paramagnetic nature of these complexes. Copper(III) is isoelectronic with nickel(II) having a 3d⁸ configuration.

The anomalous magnetic behaviour of the trivalent copper complexes can be attributed⁹⁻¹¹ to the existence of an equilibrium mixture of paramagnetic tetrahedral and diamagnetic square planar isomers in the same crystalline substance as is found

in some nickel(II) complexes. This may be due¹² to the thermal population of low-lying triplet state of Cu(III) resulting in the magnetic cross-over between the singlet and the triplet ground state. The μ_{eff} values of 2.41 and 2.32 B.M. for the complexes, [Ni(pn)₂Cl₂]Cl.2H₂O and [Ni(pn)₂Cl₂]Br.2H₂O fall within the range 1.9-2.5 B.M., as expected^{13,14} for low spin nickel(III) complexes containing one unpaired electron with considerable orbital contribution. The complexes of the type [Ni(mdtc)₂]X show room temperature magnetic moments of 2.35-2.47 B.M. corresponding to square planar¹⁵⁻¹⁶ geometry around Ni³⁺ ion which is isoelectronic with divalent cobalt.

Infrared spectra: Some of the important ir bands for the complexes with probable assignments are given in Table 2. The bands observed at ~ 1500 , 1010 and 405 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of the dithiocarbamate complexes are assigned to $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu_{as}(C-S)$ and $\nu(M-S)$, respectively. The $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(M-S)$ bands in case of divalent nickel complexes are

observed at ~ 1480 and ~ 380 cm^{-1} and the shifting of these bands to higher frequencies namely 1500 and 405 cm^{-1} suggest a higher oxidation state of the metal ion. This is consistent with the possible shortening of C=N and M-S bond lengths and follow the general pattern already noticed^{1,17-21} for other oxidised transition metal dithiocarbamate complexes. The C=S stretching frequency²²⁻²⁴ has been used to distinguish between uni and bidentate nature of dithiocarbamate. The occurrence of a single band around 1010 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in all our dithiocarbamate complexes shows the uninegative bidentate behaviour of morpholine dithiocarbamate. In the ir spectra of the propylene diamine complexes, the bands in the region 3300-3170 and 430 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$, respectively. The shifting of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ to higher frequency (~ 430 cm^{-1}) is indicative of the existence of the metal ion in the higher oxidation state. Besides, in the ir spectra of propylene diamine complexes of Ni(III), broad humps are observed at 3410, 1600 and 3440, 1600 cm^{-1} , respectively which can be assigned²⁵ to lattice water. Thermal decomposition of these two complexes reveals weight loss at 110° corresponding to two water molecules. This indicates that the water molecules are present as lattice water.

Electronic spectra : Copper(III) is isoelectronic with nickel(II). It is reported that tetrahedral^{11,26} nickel(II) complexes give electronic spectral bands at 600 and 900 nm whereas square planar^{27,28} complexes absorb in the region 400 and 600 nm. All the complexes of copper(III) reported in the present investigation exhibit bands around 400, 600 and 900 nm indicating a mixture of tetrahedral and planar forms of the complexes. Propylene diamine complexes of nickel(III) display bands around 400, 430 and 630 nm indicating¹⁴ octahedral environment around nickel(III). The presence of bands around 390, 660 and 865 nm in the dithiocarbamate complexes of nickel(III) provides definite evidence for their square planar geometry^{29,30}.

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